

EFFECT OF YARN TWIST ON THE ELASTIC PROPERTY OF COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The elastic constants of twisted yarn composites are predicted based upon the unit cell structure, and volume averaging of elastic constants of constituent materials. The geometric model predicts yarn twist angle and fiber packing fraction, which is defined as the fiber volume fraction in the twisted yarn. For the correlation of analytic results with experiments, composite samples of various yarn twist angles were tested. The samples were fabricated by a pultrusion process using glass yarns and vinylester resin. The prediction of three-dimensional elastic constants provides valuable input for the analytic characterization of textile composites made of twisted yarns.

INTRODUCTION

The development of innovative fiber architecture and textile manufacturing technology has significantly expanded the potential of fiber reinforced composites. An emerging area is textile composites reinforced with three-dimensional preforms such as woven, braided, and knitted fabrics. The integrated fiber network provides stiffness and strength in the thickness direction, thus reducing the potential for interlaminar failure, which frequently occurs in conventional laminated composites [1].

In textile preforms, yarns are often twisted for avoiding damage due to the fabrication process[2]. This is because the tows, which are assemblies of parallel filaments, have no lateral cohesion and can easily separate into individual filaments or bundles. A twisted yarn under tension induces internal force in the transverse direction, which in turn generates frictional forces among the fibers.

The Young's modulus of a twisted yarn has been obtained by several researchers [3,4], but the analyses were based on the mechanics of a fiber system. A simple relation between the fiber and yarn properties was given as $E_y = E_f \cos^4\theta$, in which, E_y and E_f are the Young's moduli of the yarn and the fiber, respectively, and θ is the twist angle. It should be noted that the deformability of a fabric is provided through the movement of individual fibers which is restricted only by the friction between neighboring fibers. When the fabric is embedded in a matrix, its deformability is greatly reduced. Therefore, the above equation is not quite useful in

the composite. Thus, the objective of this study is to investigate the effect of yarn twist on the elastic properties of composites.

GEOMETRY OF TWISTED YARNS

The geometry of twisted yarns can be described by the twist angle and the number of yarns twisted. Figure 1 shows the ideal yarn path the geometry of a helical yarn where the cylindrical yarn assembly is unfolded. Denoting the pitch length and the diameter of a twisted yarn as h and D , respectively, the twist angle(θ) is expressed as:

$$\tan\theta = \frac{\pi D}{h} \quad (1)$$

The pitch length can be calculated from the number of twists per unit length of the yarn, which is provided from manufacturer's data, and D is measured from microscopic examination. The diameter of an individual yarn(d) in the twisted yarn is expressed as:

$$d = \sqrt{\frac{4\lambda}{\pi\kappa\rho n}} \quad (2)$$

where, λ = linear density of a twisted yarn (kg/m), κ = fiber packing fraction, ρ = fiber density (kg/m³), n = number of yarns in the twisted yarn. The fiber packing fraction is defined as the fiber volume fraction in a yarn. Although κ can be obtained by observing the cross-section of the yarn, it is difficult to measure because the cross-sectional boundary of individual yarns in a twisted yarn is indiscernible. Thus, κ should be analytically predicted and this is described in the following.

Assuming the cross-section of an individual yarn is circular and the yarns are in contact with one another, the cross-section of a twisted yarn can be depicted as in Fig. 2. The following geometric relation can be obtained.

$$D = r_n d \quad (3)$$

where, n is defined above, and r_n has the following values:

$$r_2 = 2, \quad r_3 = 1 + \sqrt{2}, \quad r_4 = 1 + 2/\sqrt{3} \quad (4)$$

From Eqns. (1),(2), and (3), the fiber packing fraction is obtained as:

$$\kappa = \left(\frac{r_n}{h \tan\theta}\right)^2 \frac{4\pi\lambda}{\rho n} \quad (5)$$

TWISTED YARN COMPOSITES

The elastic response of twisted yarn composites can be predicted from yarn properties by averaging the stiffness or compliance of each yarn through coordinate transformations [5]. Figure 3 shows a twisted yarn composite with four fiber bundles. Regardless of the number of yarn bundles, it is sufficient to consider one yarn in a length of one turn to determine its elastic property. The twist angle of a yarn is denoted as θ , and an infinitesimal yarn segment can be defined by the circumferential angles ϕ and $d\phi$.

For the infinitesimal segment, fibers are assumed to align along the axial direction. Thus, the composite cylinder is transversely isotropic, and its compliance matrix is expressed as

$$[S] = \begin{pmatrix} 1/E_{11} & -\nu_{21}/E_{22} & -\nu_{21}/E_{22} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\nu_{12}/E_{11} & 1/E_{22} & -\nu_{32}/E_{22} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\nu_{12}/E_{11} & -\nu_{23}/E_{22} & 1/E_{22} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1/G_{23} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1/G_{12} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1/G_{12} \end{pmatrix} \quad (6)$$

The Young's and shear moduli are obtained from the fiber and matrix properties using micro-mechanics analysis [6]. The fiber packing fraction, κ , is used as the fiber volume fraction for the calculation.

The direction cosines between the reference coordinate system, x-y-z, and the 1-2-3 coordinate system associated with the unidirectional composite can be established. Then the properties of a yarn referring to the x-y-z system are deduced by transforming the stresses and strains via the generalized transformation matrix [7].

$$[T] = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_1^2 & \alpha_2^2 & \alpha_3^2 & 2\alpha_2\alpha_3 & 2\alpha_3\alpha_1 & 2\alpha_1\alpha_2 \\ \beta_1^2 & \beta_2^2 & \beta_3^2 & 2\beta_2\beta_3 & 2\beta_3\beta_1 & 2\beta_1\beta_2 \\ \gamma_1^2 & \gamma_2^2 & \gamma_3^2 & 2\gamma_2\gamma_3 & 2\gamma_3\gamma_1 & 2\gamma_1\gamma_2 \\ \beta_1\gamma_1 & \beta_2\gamma_2 & \beta_3\gamma_3 & \beta_2\gamma_3 + \beta_3\gamma_2 & \beta_1\gamma_3 + \beta_3\gamma_1 & \beta_1\gamma_2 + \beta_2\gamma_1 \\ \gamma_1\alpha_1 & \gamma_2\alpha_2 & \gamma_3\alpha_3 & \gamma_2\alpha_3 + \gamma_3\alpha_2 & \gamma_1\alpha_3 + \gamma_3\alpha_1 & \gamma_1\alpha_2 + \gamma_2\alpha_1 \\ \alpha_1\beta_1 & \alpha_2\beta_2 & \alpha_3\beta_3 & \alpha_2\beta_3 + \alpha_3\beta_2 & \alpha_1\beta_3 + \alpha_3\beta_1 & \alpha_1\beta_2 + \alpha_2\beta_1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (7)$$

where α , β , and γ with subscripts are direction cosines and are defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_1 &= \cos(1,x) & \alpha_2 &= \cos(1,y) & \alpha_3 &= \cos(1,z) \\ \beta_1 &= \cos(2,x) & \beta_2 &= \cos(2,y) & \beta_3 &= \cos(2,z) \\ \gamma_1 &= \cos(3,x) & \gamma_2 &= \cos(3,y) & \gamma_3 &= \cos(3,z) \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

By setting the 1-2-3 coordinate with the 3-axis perpendicular to the x-axis, the direction cosines are simplified as:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_1 &= \cos\theta & \alpha_2 &= -\sin\theta \sin\phi & \alpha_3 &= \sin\theta \cos\phi \\ \beta_1 &= \sin\theta & \beta_2 &= \cos\theta \sin\phi & \beta_3 &= -\cos\theta \cos\phi \\ \gamma_1 &= 0 & \gamma_2 &= \cos\phi, & \gamma_3 &= \sin\phi \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Thus, the compliance matrix of the unidirectional composite cylinder [S], referring to the 1-2-3 coordinate system, is transformed to [S'], referring to the xyz coordinate system.

$$[S'] = [T]^t [S] [T] \quad (10)$$

where $[T]^t$ is a transpose matrix of [T]. Although all 21 components of S'_{ij} can be obtained in terms of θ and ϕ , only six of them are expressed as follows because a twisted yarn composite is a transversely isotropic material.

$$\begin{aligned}
 S'_{11} &= S_{11}\cos^4\theta + S_{22}\sin^4\theta + (2S_{12} + S_{66})\cos^2\theta \sin^2\theta \\
 S'_{12} &= [S_{11} + S_{22} - S_{66}]\cos^2\theta \sin^2\theta \sin^2\phi + S_{12}(\cos^4\theta + \sin^4\theta)\sin^2\phi \\
 &\quad + (S_{12}\cos^2\theta + S_{23}\sin^2\theta)\cos^2\phi \\
 S'_{22} &= S_{11}\sin^4\theta \sin^4\phi + (2S_{12} + S_{66})\sin^2\theta \sin^2\phi(\cos^2\theta \sin^2\phi + \cos^2\phi) \\
 &\quad + S_{22}(\cos^4\theta \sin^4\phi + \cos^4\phi) + (2S_{23} + S_{44})\cos^2\theta \cos^2\phi \sin^2\phi \\
 S'_{23} &= [S_{11}\sin^4\theta + 2S_{12}\cos^2\theta \sin^2\theta + (1 + \cos^4\theta)S_{22} - S_{44}\cos^2\theta \\
 &\quad - S_{66}\sin^4\theta] \cos^2\phi \sin^2\phi + (S_{12}\sin^2\theta + S_{23}\cos^2\theta)(\cos^4\phi + \sin^4\phi) \\
 S'_{44} &= 4 [S_{11}\sin^4\theta - 2S_{12}\sin^4\theta + S_{22}(1 + \cos^4\theta) - 2S_{23}\cos^2\theta \\
 &\quad + S_{66}\cos^2\theta \sin^2\theta] \cos^2\phi \sin^2\phi + (S_{44}\cos^2\theta + S_{66}\sin^2\theta)\cos^2(2\phi) \\
 S'_{55} &= 4(S_{11} - 2S_{12} + S_{22})\cos^2\theta \sin^2\theta \cos^2\phi + S_{66}\cos^2(2\theta)\cos^2\phi \\
 &\quad + (S_{44}\sin^2\theta + S_{66}\cos^2\theta)\sin^2\phi
 \end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

Since the composite yarn consists of the infinitesimal segments in series, the iso-stress condition can be assumed, and the compliances are averaged through one turn of the twist from $\phi=0$ to $\phi=2\pi$:

$$S^a_{ij} = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} S'_{ij} d\phi \quad (i,j=1-6) \tag{12}$$

Carrying out the integration, the six independent compliance constants are obtained as functions of θ only:

$$\begin{aligned}
 S^a_{11} &= S_{11}\cos^4\theta + S_{22}\sin^4\theta + (2S_{12} + S_{66})\cos^2\theta \sin^2\theta \\
 S^a_{12} &= S^a_{13} = \frac{1}{2} [(S_{11} + S_{22} - S_{66})\cos^2\theta \sin^2\theta \\
 &\quad + S_{12}(\cos^4\theta + \sin^4\theta + \cos^2\theta) + S_{23}\sin^2\theta] \\
 S^a_{22} &= S^a_{33} = \frac{1}{8} [3S_{11}\sin^4\theta + (2S_{12} + S_{66})\sin^2\theta(1 + 3\cos^2\theta) \\
 &\quad + 3S_{22}(1 + \cos^4\theta) + (2S_{23} + S_{44})\cos^2\theta] \\
 S^a_{23} &= \frac{1}{8} [S_{11}\sin^4\theta + 2S_{12}\cos^2\theta \sin^2\theta + S_{22}(1 + \cos^4\theta) \\
 &\quad - S_{44}\cos^2\theta - S_{66}\sin^4\theta + 6(S_{12}\sin^2\theta + S_{23}\cos^2\theta)] \\
 S^a_{44} &= \frac{1}{2} [(S_{11} - 2S_{12})\sin^4\theta + S_{22}(1 + \cos^4\theta) \\
 &\quad + (S_{44} - 2S_{23})\cos^2\theta + S_{66}\sin^2\theta(1 + \cos^2\theta)] \\
 S^a_{55} &= S^a_{66} = 2(S_{11} - 2S_{12} + S_{22})\cos^2\theta \sin^2\theta \\
 &\quad + \frac{1}{2} [S_{44}\sin^2\theta + S_{66}(\cos^2(2\theta) + \cos^2\theta)]
 \end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

Finally, the engineering elastic constants of the twisted yarn composite are determined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_{xx} &= 1/S^a_{11}, \quad E_{yy} = 1/S^a_{22}, \quad E_{zz} = 1/S^a_{33} \\
 G_{yz} &= 1/S^a_{44}, \quad G_{xz} = 1/S^a_{55}, \quad G_{xy} = 1/S^a_{66} \\
 \nu_{xy} &= -S^a_{12}/S^a_{11}, \quad \nu_{zx} = -S^a_{13}/S^a_{22}, \quad \nu_{yz} = -S^a_{23}/S^a_{22}
 \end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

CORRELATIONS

In order to verify the analytic characterization of twisted yarn composites, tensile tests have been conducted. The specimens are fabricated by a pultrusion process utilizing three types of twisted glass yarns and vinylester. The curing temperature was 165 °C, and curing time was 8 minutes. The specimen size was 250 mm x 12.7 mm x 1.7 mm. The fiber volume fraction was measured by the ignition method. Five specimens of each type of twisted yarns were tested, and Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio were measured.

Table 1 and 2 summarize the material input data and model predictions. It is noted that the model provides predictions of all the three-dimensional engineering constants.

Table 1: Summary of geometric and physical input data and predictions.

	Number of Twisted Yarns (n)		
	2	3	4
Input Data			
Yarn diameter, D (mm)	0.47	0.55	0.65
Pitch length, h (mm)	6.7	6.7	6.7
Density, ρ (kg/m ³)	2560	2560	2560
Linear density, λ (g/m)	0.1967	0.3383	0.4537
Geometric Prediction			
Twist angle, θ (degree)	12.4	14.5	18
Fiber packing fraction, κ	0.89	0.86	0.79

Table 2: Summary of elastic property input data and model predictions for the twisted yarn composites.

Elastic Property Data	Engineering Constants	n = 2 (GPa)	n = 3 (GPa)	n = 4 (GPa)
Glass fiber	E _{xx}	56.7	49.3	36.3
E _{1f} = E _{2f} = 76 GPa	E _{yy} = E _{zz}	25.7	21.4	14.9
G _{12f} = G _{23f} = 30 GPa	G _{xy} = G _{zx}	9.96	8.48	6.03
v ₁₂ = 0.28	G _{yz}	9.61	8.05	5.59
Vinylester	v _{xy}	0.31	0.30	0.33
E _m = 4 GPa, v _m = 0.38	v _{yz}	0.14	0.13	0.14
	v _{zx}	0.34	0.33	0.33

For the correlation between the elastic constants of twisted yarn composites and those of pultruded composites, the volumetric correction factor ($V_r = V_f / \kappa$) is introduced, where V_f is fiber volume fraction of specimens. The longitudinal Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio of specimens can be expressed in terms of those of twisted yarn and matrix material using the rule-of-mixtures:

$$E_p = E_t V_r + E_m(1-V_r) \tag{15}$$

$$v_p = v_t V_r + v_m(1-V_r) \tag{16}$$

where, subscripts p and t mean pultruded composites and twisted composites, respectively.

Table 3 summarizes the comparison of engineering constants for model prediction and test results. The values in the parentheses are standard deviations. The comparison shows good agreements between the model prediction and test results.

Table 3: Comparison of engineering constants of model predictions and test results.

Engineering Constants	n = 2		n = 3		n = 4	
	pred.	tests	pred.	tests	pred.	tests
Young's modulus, E_p (GPa)	39.4	43.8 (± 1.8)	37.1	41.9 (± 2.4)	31.4	35.4 (± 1.5)
Poisson's ratio, ν_p	0.33	0.30 (± 0.02)	0.32	0.31 (± 0.02)	0.34	0.32 (± 0.06)
Fiber volume fraction, V_f	0.60		0.63		0.66	

CONCLUSIONS

- (1) The geometric model for and the prediction of yarn twist angle, fiber packing fraction, and elastic constants of twisted yarn composites has been developed based upon the yarn repeating geometry, coordinate transformation, and volume averaging of elastic constants of constituent materials.
- (2) For the correlation of analytic results with experiments, composite specimens of three different yarn twist angles were fabricated by a pultrusion process and tensile tests were conducted. The correlations of longitudinal Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio between model predictions and test results showed reasonably good agreements.
- (3) The model can provide the predictions of three-dimensional engineering constants, which are valuable input data for the analytic characterization of textile composites made of twisted yarns.

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Figure 1: A twisted yarn and its unfolded geometry.

Figure 2 : Idealized cross-sections of twisted yarns: (a) $n = 2$; (b) $n = 3$; (c) $n = 4$.

Figure 3: Coordinate system for an infinitesimal element of a twisted yarn composite.

